

PERSPEKTIF PENDIDIKAN KARAKTER AKHLAK MULIA PADA PERUBAHAN TINGKAH LAKU SISWA

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk mendapatkan informasi penerapan pendidikan karakter akhlak mulia sebagai upaya pembentukan karakter siswa. Penelitian menggunakan metode deskriptif kualitatif. Subjek penelitian yaitu siswa jurusan Teknik Mesin SMK Negeri 1 Tanjung Raya Kabupaten Agam Provinsi Sumatera Barat. Pemilihan subjek penelitian didasari kolaborasi penerapan program penanaman nilai rohani yang dilakukan ketua jurusan. Teknik pengambilan data dilakukan dengan observasi dan wawancara. Teknik analisis data menggunakan analisis deskriptif. Hasil penelitian mengungkapkan bahwa program pelaksanaan salat Zuhur berjemaah disambut positif oleh siswa; siswa telah patuh terhadap peraturan yang ada di sekolah; siswa lebih mementingkan perintah orang tua walaupun sedang asyik bermain dengan temannya; siswa memiliki respek terhadap lingkungan masyarakat; dan siswa memiliki jiwa cinta alam dan berbudaya menjaga lingkungan.

Kata Kunci: pendidikan karakter, akhlak mulia, perubahan tingkah laku.

Abstract

The research aimed to obtain information on the application of moral character education as an effort to build student character. This research used a qualitative descriptive method. The research subjects were students majoring in Mechanical Engineering at SMK Negeri 1 Tanjung Raya Agam Regency, West Sumatra Province. The selection of research subjects was based on collaborative implementation of the spiritual value cultivation program carried out by the head of the department. The data collection technique was carried out by observation and interviews. The data analysis technique used descriptive analysis. The results of the research revealed that the Zuhur prayer program in congregation was positively welcomed by the students; students have obeyed the rules in school; students are more concerned with parental orders even though they are enjoying playing with their friends; students have respect for the community environment; and students have a spirit of love for nature and a culture of protecting the environment.

Keywords: character education, noble morals, change in behavior.